

Fluorescent dye transport assay for SLC1A3 using HEK JumpIn SLC1A3 OE cells

PubChem AID: 1745864

Authors	Sara Tremolada ¹ , Lia Scarabottolo ¹
Affiliations	¹ Axxam S.p.A., OpenZone - via A. Meucci, 3 – 20091 Bresso (Milan, Italy)

Assay description

Purpose of the assay is to determine the functionality of the SLC1A3 transporter, stably expressed in the HEK-293 JumpIn TReX cell line (SLC1A3 OverExpressing - OE - cell line). SLC1A3 (EAAT1) is a sodium-dependent, high-affinity amino acid transporter that mediates the uptake of L-glutamate, L-aspartate, and L-Cysteine. It plays an essential role in transporting these amino acids across plasma membrane in neurons, and it functions as a symporter that co-transportes one amino acid together with 2 or 3 Na⁺ ions. The transport mediated by SLC1A3 is therefore electrogenic. For this reason, the HEK-293 JumpIn TReX/SLC1A3 OE cell line was tested using the Membrane Potential (MP) dye read-out, which is described in the section below.

Assay protocol

FLIPR Membrane Potential (MP) dye is a lipophilic, anionic, bis-oxonol dye from Molecular Devices, able to cross the plasma membrane and to measure voltage changes by its potential-dependent accumulation and redistribution. When cells are depolarized, the dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye exit and decreased fluorescence. This read-out is compatible with high-throughput applications. A general protocol for the use of MP dye requires to discard cell medium and load the cells with the dye dissolved in a suitable buffer for a period that typically ranges from 10-15 minutes to 1 hour. Then the dye has to be excited with the proper wavelength and the emission is acquired. Detection of fluorescent emission is achieved by means of a fluorescent plate reader (such as FLIPR^{TETRA} or Hamamatsu FDSS), able to excite the probe and to read its emission.

The specific protocol that was used for the HEK-293 JumpIn TReX/SLC1A3 OE cell line is reported below in details:

- Cell lines: HEK293 JumpIn TReX/SLC1A3 OE; HEK293 JumpIn TReX WT (used as control)
- Cells seeding: 10.000 c/w in 384-well plates (black, clear bottom, poly-Lys coated). Induction was carried out adding 1 µg/mL Doxycycline during seeding procedure (24h adhesion)
- Read-out: MP dye
- Dye loading: after medium manual discard, cells were loaded with 20 µL/w of MP dye (1X) dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer (Tyrode's Buffer: 130 mM NaCl, 5 mM KCl, 2 mM CaCl₂, 5 mM NaHCO₃, 1 mM MgCl₂, 20 mM HEPES, pH 7.4) and incubated for 30 min at RT
- Substrates' injection: after incubation with MP dye, substrates were injected (20 µL/w, 2X) using FLIPR^{TETRA} plate reader and fluorescence was recorded by the instrument for 5 min using the following Excitation/Emission filters: exc. 510-545 nm, em. 565-625 nm. The substrates used were L-Glutamic Acid, L-Aspartic Acid, and L-Cysteine. All the stimuli were dissolved in standard Tyrode's buffer and injected at different concentrations, to determine the dose-dependency of the SLC1A3 response (for each substrate, top concentration started from 3 mM, and was followed by a semi-log dilution step)
- Data Export: FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates (quadruplicates) were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained as raw data by applying the "Response Over Baseline" and "Substract Background" corrections at a reading step before injection. Data were then exported as Maximum (MAX) signal for the entire kinetic after the injection. Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves with GraphPad PRISM software.

Additional information

Not available

Target data

SLC	SLC1A3
Synonyms	EAAT1 (Excitatory amino acid transporter 1)
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 1 (Glial High Affinity Glutamate Transporter)
UniProt ID	Canonical form (Isoform 1, identifier: P43003-1)
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE029W-F (HEK-SLC1A3-WTOE-p1)

Assay data

<p>L-Glutamic acid MP dye incubation in Tyrode's standard</p> <p>EC50=16 μM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> —○— SLC1A3 not treated —■— SLC1A3 doxy-treated —◇— WT not treated —○— WT doxy-treated 	Compound name (1)	L-Glutamic Acid
	PubChem CID	33032
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma cat. G1251
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC50= 16 μM
<p>L-Aspartic acid MP dye incubation in Tyrode's standard</p> <p>EC50=15 μM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> —○— SLC1A3 not treated —■— SLC1A3 doxy-treated —◇— WT not treated —○— WT doxy-treated 	Compound name (2)	L-Aspartic Acid
	PubChem CID	5960
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma cat. A9256
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC50= 15 μM
<p>L-Cysteine MP dye incubation in Tyrode's standard</p> <p>EC50=376 μM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> —○— SLC1A3 not treated —■— SLC1A3 doxy-treated —◇— WT not treated —○— WT doxy-treated 	Compound name (3)	L-Cysteine
	PubChem CID	5862
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma cat. W326305
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC50= 376 μM

Discussion

A strong, dose-dependent and specific increase of the fluorescent signal (due to sodium influx) was detected upon injection of L-Glutamic Acid, L-Aspartic Acid, and L-Cysteine, after induction of target expression with Doxycycline for 24h. This cell-based assay was therefore functionally validated using MP dye as read-out.

Cross references

- *RESOLUTE* report at [Zenodo](#).